

DO PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS' LEVELS OF ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION INFLUENCE THEIR ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT GOAL ORIENTATION?

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the influence of pre-service teachers' levels of academic procrastination on their academic achievement goal orientation. Survey data were collected from 245 pre-service teachers studying in different B.Ed colleges of Sambalpur University of Odisha. Academic Achievement Goal Orientation Scale designed and standardized by Christopher Was (2006) and adapted version of Tuckman Procrastination Scale (2003) were used for the collection of data. Findings indicated a significant correlation between academic procrastination and academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers. Implications of academic procrastination on academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers were suggested.

Keywords: *academic procrastination, academic achievement goal orientation, pre-service teachers.*

1. Conceptualization of the Problem

In today's rapidly evolving educational landscape, the role of teachers, particularly pre-service teachers, holds paramount importance in shaping the future of education. Pre-service teachers, those undergoing teacher training programs, represent the next generation of educators who will guide and inspire students in their academic journeys. As such, understanding the factors that influence pre-service teachers' academic behaviors and attitudes is crucial for ensuring effective teaching practices and fostering positive learning outcomes.

One such factor that has garnered increasing attention in educational research is academic procrastination. Academic procrastination refers to the tendency to delay the initiation or completion of academic tasks despite knowing the negative consequences associated with such delay (Ferrari, 2010). Academic activities that students put off include completion of assignments and projects, and exam and course preparation (Pychyl et al., 2000; Orpen, 1998; Zarick and Stonebraker, 2009). It is a prevalent issue among students across various educational levels and has been linked to lower academic performance, increased stress, and decreased overall well-being (Ajaye & Osiki, 2008). Despite its detrimental effects, academic procrastination remains a pervasive challenge in educational settings (Eugene and Kurtca, 2020).

Concurrently, another construct that significantly impacts academic performance and learning is achievement goal orientation. Achievement goal orientation refers to individuals' underlying cognitive frameworks or orientations toward achieving competence and mastery in academic endeavors (Printrich, 2000). This framework comprises different goal orientations, such as mastery goals (focused on learning and improvement) and performance goals (focused on demonstrating competence relative to others) (Neubert, 1998). Achievement goal orientation plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' motivation, persistence, and approach to learning tasks (Ludwig & Geller 2000).

While both academic procrastination and achievement goal orientation have been extensively studied in student populations, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding their relationship among pre-service teachers. Understanding how pre-service teachers' tendencies to procrastinate academically may influence their goal orientations is essential for informing teacher education programs and developing targeted interventions to support pre-service teachers' professional development.

Therefore, this research seeks to address this gap by investigating the relationship between pre-service teachers' levels of academic procrastination and their academic achievement goal orientation. By examining this relationship, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the factors influencing pre-service teachers' academic behaviors and attitudes, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of teacher education programs and the promotion of effective teaching practices. The present study will assess the following questions:

1. What is the level of academic procrastination of the pre-service teachers?

2. What is the level of academic achievement goal orientation of the pre-service teachers?
3. Do pre-service teachers' levels of academic procrastination influence their academic achievement goal orientation?

2. Objectives of the Study: The investigator seeks to meet the following research objectives in this study.

1. To study the academic procrastination of pre-service teachers.
2. To study the academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers.
3. To study the relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers.

3. Hypotheses of the Study

Based on the research objectives, the following null hypothesis was formulated.

1. There is no significant relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers

4. Procedure: Descriptive survey method was employed to find out the influence of pre-service teachers' levels of academic procrastination on their academic achievement goal orientation. The study involved 245 pre-service teachers (121 male and 124 female pre-service teachers) as sample. They were selected randomly from three B.Ed colleges of Sambalpur University, Odisha.

Adapted version of Tuckman Procrastination Scale TPS of Tuckman (2003) was used to ascertain the academic procrastination of pre-service teachers. The scale consists of 48 items with both "true keyed" and "false keyed" items. Each statement has five alternatives (Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Undecided, Agree, Strongly Agree) from which a respondent has to choose any one, which candidly express his response. The scale value for five alternatives are 1- Strongly Disagree, 2- Disagree, 3-Undecided, 4- Agree, 5-Strongly Agree. Individual score was obtained by adding all scale value. The validity of the original scale was 0.91. For reliability, Cronbachs Alpha was calculated, which ranges from .68 to .88.

Academic achievement goal orientation scale by Christopher Was (2006) was used to ascertain the academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers. The scale was consisted of 34 items covering four dimensions namely, Mastery orientation, Performance approach, Performance avoidant and Work avoidant. Each statement had six alternatives (Very Untrue, Mostly Untrue, Somewhat Untrue, Somewhat True, Mostly True and Very True) from which a respondent has to choose anyone, which candidly express his response.

The demographic data of the participants were gathered via the information sheet. In the information sheet data of the pre-service teachers i.e., their name, gender, stream, locality, date of birth, and academic achievement were included.

The collected data were analyzed by using percentage, and correlation and accordingly interpretation were made.

5. Analysis and Interpretation: First objective of the study was to study the academic procrastination of pre-service teachers. For this, investigator categorized pupil teachers as High, Moderate and Low level of academic procrastination on the basis of score. Table-1 presents number and percentage of pre-service teachers belonging to different level of academic procrastination.

Table-1: Academic Procrastination of Pre-service teachers (N=245)

Scores	Classification	Pre-service teachers	
		No.	%
Above 140	High level of procrastination	91	37
125-140	Medium level of procrastination	86	35
Below 125	Low level of procrastination	68	28

From table-1 it is apparent that out of total 245 pupil teachers 91 pupil teachers i.e. 37% have high levels of procrastination who score more than 140, 86 pupil teachers i.e. 35% have middle levels of procrastination whose score fall in between 125-140 and the rest of 68 pupil teachers i.e. 28% have low levels of procrastination who score less than 125. These results suggest that 72% of pupil teacher have different levels of difficulties in academic procrastination.

Second objective of the study was to study the academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers. The objective is analyzed as follows. Table-2 presents number and percentage of pre-service teachers belonging to different level of academic achievement goal orientation.

Table- 2: Academic Achievement Goal Orientation of Pre-Service Teachers (N=245)

Scores	Classification	Pre-service teachers	
		No.	%
Above 141	Highly academic achievement goal oriented	91	37
120-140	Moderately academic achievement goal oriented	95	39
Below 120	Less academic achievement goal oriented	59	24

From table-2 it is apparent that out of total 245 pre-service teachers 91 pre-service teachers i.e. 37% are highly academic achievement goal oriented who score more than 141, 95 pre-service teachers i.e. 39% are moderately academic achievement goal oriented who score in between 120-141 and the rest 59 pre-service teachers i.e. 24% are less academic achievement goal oriented who score less than 120.

Third objective of the study was to study the relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers. The objective is analyzed as follows. Table-3 presents the relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers.

Table- 3: Correlation between Academic Procrastination and Academic Achievement Goal-Orientation

Variable	N	df	r value	Level of significance
AP and AAG	245	243	-.45	Significant at .01 level
AP and mastery orientation			-.47	Significant at .01 level
AP and performance approach			-.44	Significant at .01 level
AP and performance avoidant			.36	Significant at .01 level
AP and work avoidant			.19	Not significant at .05 level

It is observed from the table-3 that the coefficient of correlation between academic procrastination and academic achievement goal-orientation of pre-service teachers is -.45 which is negative and significant at .01 level. It means that the hypothesis, there exists significant relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement goal orientation of pre-service teachers is accepted.

The co-efficient correlation of academic procrastination with mastery orientation and performance approach orientation of pre-service teachers are -.47 and -.44 respectively which are negative and significant at .01 level. It means procrastination related negatively to mastery and performance goal orientation of pre-service teachers. But the co-efficient correlation of academic procrastination with performance avoidance and work avoidance of pre-service teachers are .36 and .19 respectively. It revealed that procrastination related positively to performance avoidance but there is no relation between academic procrastination and work avoidance orientation of pre-service teachers.

6. Results and Discussion

Findings obtained from the present investigation indicated that 37% pre-service teachers as high academic procrastinators and 35% as moderate academic procrastinators. It

means that most of the pre-service teachers have different levels of difficulties in academic procrastination. Literature review found that there are different findings obtained by various researches. (Ozer & Yetkin, 2018; Varul & Gundung, 2019; Balakic & Duru, 2009) have found academic procrastination among pre-service teacher which are similar with the results of present study and another study found that the level of pre-service teachers' academic procrastination is quite low (Akdemir, 2019). The result of present study may be due to the fact that work load, assignment, lack of time management, achievement motivation, self-discipline; and higher level of impulsivity, poor study habits of pre-service teachers. Furthermore this study reported 37% pupil- teachers have high academic achievement goal orientation and 39% pre-service teachers have moderate academic achievement goal orientation behaviour.

The findings pattern to the relationship of academic procrastination with mastery orientation and performance approach of the pre-service teachers in the present study revealed that significant negative relation. This result of the present study has resemblance with other studies in the field (Moller and Elliot 2000, Howell and Watson 2007, Scher and Osterman 2002, Jeannetta et al 2008). This finding suggests that students who adopted the goal of learning everything there is to learn tended not to procrastinate.

Another finding of the present study regarding the relationship between academic procrastination and performance avoidance revealed that procrastination behaviour is positively correlated with performance avoidance goal orientation. This result of the present study is parallel with the study conducted by (Tuckman 1991, Rhodewalt 1994, Mc Gregor and Elliot 2002, Wolter 2003, 2004). This finding seems meaningful that pupil-teacher adopted the goal of avoiding performance tended to procrastinate. The analysis also indicates that there is no relation between academic procrastination and work-avoidance goal orientation of pre-service teachers. This result of the present study resembles the result of the study conducted by (Rhodewalt 1994, Elliot & Mc Gregor 2001, Wolter 2003 and Howell Watson 2007).

7. Educational Implication

The findings of the present study have a number of practical implications for both educational theory and practice. Gaining a better understanding of the correlates and practice of pre-service teachers' procrastination is a helpful first step in providing academic support to pre-service teachers. Students may be actually aware of their procrastination tendency and educators can actively create environment that could increase productivity and efficiency,

thus greatly reducing the problem of delaying completion of academic work. Tasks aimed to instill in students the skills of self-arrangement and time management may serve to decrease procrastination behaviour. Therefore, it is thought that organizing group work which aims to equip students with the skills and habits of effective time management, planned study and sensible expectations for academic work and problem solving will be beneficial in decreasing the level of procrastination tendency in students. Another implication of present study is teaching pre-service teacher to set specific proximal goals for their academic work. If administrators, policy makers and other instructors wish to improve the achievement levels and the general satisfaction of students, they may be well advised to screen and inspire the type of goals their student pursue. Given that students can and do pursue multiple goals, it is important to understand how different type of achievement goals interact to influence achievement and satisfaction. Therefore knowledge on how goal orientation develops, changes and how it affects motivational and educational outcomes will be tremendously useful to everybody who is involved in shaping and improving the academic learning environment.

8. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research study has provided valuable insights into the complex interplay between academic procrastination and achievement goal orientation among pre-service teachers. By examining these constructs, the study has contributed to our understanding of the factors influencing pre-service teachers' academic behaviors, motivations, and professional development.

It is evident from the findings that addressing academic procrastination and promoting adaptive achievement goal orientations are essential components of effective pre-service teacher education. Teacher education programs must incorporate strategies to help pre-service teachers recognize and overcome procrastination tendencies, develop effective time management skills, and cultivate a growth-oriented mindset focused on continuous learning and improvement.

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